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Robotic Hummingbird: A Flapping Wing Micro Air Vehicle

MASTER'S DEGREE THESIS

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Dedicated to my family...

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Abstract

Inspired by the amazing flight capabilities of actual hummingbirds, this thesis describes the design, construction, and testing of a robotic hummingbird, an example of a flapping wing micro air vehicle (FWMAV). The main goal is to develop a bio-inspired micro air vehicle that can replicate the intricate flying patterns of hummingbirds. The project takes a comprehensive approach, starting with the main body and wings and working its way down to the construction of the flapping wing mechanism. Prototypes are designed, created and tested to assess aerodynamic performance, lift generation, and flight stability. In order to improve the effectiveness and functionality of the FWMAV, the research investigates the integration of cutting-edge materials and control systems. The outcomes add to the expanding field of bio-inspired robotics and have potential uses in surveillance, environmental monitoring, and other domains requiring small, manoeuvrable air vehicles.

List of Abbreviations

ABS	A crylonitrile B utadiene S tylene
AI	A rtificial I ntelligence
CAD	C omputer A ided D esign
CFD	C omputational F luid D ynamics
DOF	D egree O f F reedom
FWMAV	F lapping W ing M icro A ir V ehicle
LEV	L eading E dge V ortices
MAV	M icro A ir V ehicle
PD	P roportional D erivative
SWaP	S ize W eight and P ower
TEV	T railing E dge V ortices
UAV	U nmanned A erial V ehicle
UV	U ltra V iolet
VOC	V olatile O rganic C ompounds

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Overview

The aim of this project is to design and develop a flapping wing micro air vehicle mimicking a hummingbird capable of take-off.

The key tasks of this project are as follows:

- Task 1: Design wings
- Task 2: Design hummingbird main 'body'
- Task 3: Design mechanics behind the flapping wings
- Task 4: Build prototypes
- Task 5: Test prototypes

This thesis will be split into seven chapters, each covering an aspect of the project:

- Chapter 1: Introduction. This chapter will introduce the topic and cover the background of the project.
- Chapter 2: Literature Review. This will focus on the existing literature on flapping wing micro air vehicles (FWMAVs) and assess where the challenges lie in the field. This is done to get a better understanding of the topic as well as identify gaps where more research is needed.
- Chapter 3: Theoretical Framework. This chapter will be based on the theory required to successfully build a micro air vehicle (MAV). This includes topics such as aerodynamics and kinematics.
- Chapter 4: Prototype Designs. This section of the thesis will highlight the design stage of the MAV. Each prototype design will be presented along with the rationale behind its design.

- Chapter 5: Testing and Results. This part of the thesis focuses on the successful prototype and the testing phase. The FWMAV will ideally be able to flap its wings, mimicking a hummingbird.
- Chapter 6: Discussion. The findings of the thesis will be discussed in relation to existing literature and analysed to provide key insights.
- Chapter 7: Conclusion. A conclusion of the outcome of the thesis.

1.2 Background

1.2.1 UAVs

Drones, also known as unmanned aerial vehicle (UAVs), are generally recognised for their application in the military, helping soldiers develop and monitor strategies to maximise their chances of survival. However, because of rapid advancements in contemporary technology, drones are becoming more widely used by regular people for business or leisure purposes. This covers anything from taking images and videos to use for monitoring, to delivery services for businesses like Amazon.

Types of UAVs

There are 5 different type of UAVs, each with their own design and purpose:

- Fixed-Wing. These are unmanned aerial vehicles that need a runway or a catapult in order to take off from the ground. Both their endurance and their speed are excellent attributes for this kind of UAV. Fixed-wing UAVs may also carry a larger payload and cover more areas during a single flight. But compared to the other kinds, they are more costly. [1]
- Rotary-Wing. These provide the benefits of fixed flight with the flexibility of manoeuvrability. These features can prove beneficial for a wide range of missions. Typically, they are the most extensively used UAVs across many cases and include multi-rotor and unmanned helicopters. However, they are unable to fly for extended periods of time or at very high speeds. [1]
- Blimps. This kind of UAV is larger than the others, flies at slower speeds, and is lighter than air. They are regarded as reasonably safe in the event of a collision because of their manufacturing qualities, which enable them to stay in the air even in the event of a complete loss of power. [1]
- Flapping Wing. These miniature UAVs have flexible, curved little wings that mimic the flight patterns of insects and birds. [1]
- Parafoil-Wing. These kinds of aircraft typically have one or more propellers in the back to help control their trajectory while also utilising the air's strength to propel them forward with little energy expenditure. They can also transport a heavier cargo. [1]

Applications of UAVs

As mentioned previously, UAVs were initially used as military equipment for reconnaissance missions to aid in survival tactics. However, with the continuous development of UAVs, this is no longer the case and they can be used for several other purposes. For example:

- **Agriculture.** Farmers are now using UAVs to analyse crop behaviour in large fields, such as rice, maize, and wheat. They use the drones to scan the area, take pictures, and report any peculiarities. This is an advancement over satellite-based inspections and provides more accurate data. [2] UAVs can be used in precision agriculture to gather data from ground sensors, schedule irrigation, diagnose diseases, spray pesticides, monitor and manage crops, and detect weeds. Precision agriculture using UAVs is a time and money-saving technique that can increase farming systems' profitability, productivity, and crop yields. [3]
- **Remote Sensing.** At the moment, high resolution imagery data of remote places like islands, mountaintops, and coasts are obtained using amateur drone technology. The data from airborne, space-borne, and ground-based remote sensing systems can be combined with UAV technology. UAVs' lightweight design and low cost enable high-quality, temporally and spatially resolved observation. UAVs' remote sensing capabilities can help in monitoring drought conditions, water quality, and disease detection, among other things. [3]
- **Surveillance.** UAVs are being used throughout the coasts of Australia and the United States to monitor fishing, shipping, and other coastal operations. [2] They can also be used for safety as UAVs that are affordable, dependable, and adaptable are currently making a big difference in aerial surveillance, monitoring, and surveying any given area to stop any illegal activities. [3]
- **Natural Disaster Management.** UAVs have the capability to access disaster truck sites that pose a risk to human safety in the event of a man-made or natural disaster, such as floods, tsunamis, or terrorist attacks. Such disasters have the potential to seriously harm utilities like power, water, and transportation as well as telecommunications. UAVs can assist in information gathering, provide immediate assistance when needed, and navigate debris. Rescue personnel can be helped by UAVs equipped with radars, sensors, and high-quality cameras to detect damage, initiate recovery efforts right away, and deliver resources like manned helicopters and first aid kits. [3]
- **Road Traffic Monitoring.** UAVs are becoming a viable option for gathering information regarding traffic conditions on roadways. Cost-effective drones are able to monitor vast stretches of road, in contrast to traditional monitoring gear like loop detectors, surveillance cameras, and microwave sensors. The police can also use drones to gain a clear view of traffic accidents or to conduct a thorough sweep against crimes like car theft. [3]

1.2.2 MAVs

MAVs are a type of UAV that are significantly smaller. The current target size for MAVs is about 15 centimetres, or six inches, and the creation of insect-sized aircraft is supposedly predicted in the near future. [4] Their low noise and cheap production cost make them ideal for military image capture and surveillance applications. Furthermore, they have a minimal chance of being intercepted by radar because of their miniature stature. MAVs are designed to perform a variety of tasks and may be operated remotely or independently. They are often used in the military for reconnaissance reasons. They are able to move at up to 20 m/s and can visualise day and night in real time. MAVs are also utilised in urban settings for mapping and traffic flow monitoring. [5]

There are 3 different types of MAV; fixed wing, rotary wing and flapping wing.

Fixed Wing

Fixed wing MAVs are small, autonomous aircraft that, like conventional aeroplanes, create lift with a rigid wing structure. The benefits of fixed wing MAVs include longer endurance and better payload capacities. Due to its fixed wing lifting surfaces, the vehicle's stability when confronted with wind gusts can also be adjusted to provide a more stable flight. These MAVs, however, require a considerably longer landing strip. They often have a minimal operating speed, inadequate collision avoidance capabilities, and are unable to hover. [6]

FIGURE 1.1: The Black Widow Fixed Wing MAV
[7]

Rotary Wing

Rotary wing MAVs are small, autonomous aircraft that, like multi-rotor drones or helicopters, produce lift and manoeuvrability through the use of rotors. Rotating wings can move at slower speeds and even hover. They can also do perches, which allows them to complete the task whilst using less power. Rotary wings have the ability to be made smaller, with a reduced endurance and payload which allows them to operate in limited spaces. [6]

FIGURE 1.2: Black Hornet Nano Rotary Wing MAV
[8]

Flapping Wing

Flapping wing MAVs are bioinspired aircrafts that produce lift and propulsion through the use of the flapping wings, similar to birds. They can hover and are better suited for indoor use than MAVs with rotating wings. They become harder to spot because they fly with less noise and are less impacted by being close to walls. In fact, they can collide with them and still be able to fly in a considerably smaller area with only minor damage.[6] Compared to conventional drones, their natural flying path makes it easier for them to operate stealthily and integrate into their surroundings. Even though they have specific advantages like energy conservation and mobility, their intricate design and small payload capacity can be a problem.

FIGURE 1.3: An Example of a Flapping Wing MAV
[9]

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1 The DelFly: Design, Aerodynamics, and Artificial Intelligence of a Flapping Wing Robot

2.1.1 Introduction

The prospective uses of flapping wing micro air vehicles (FWMAVs) in surveillance, environmental monitoring, and biological research has generated a lot of interest. These aircraft are designed to combine the advantages of fixed-wing and rotary-wing aircraft, emulating the flapping flying of insects and birds. The book's first few chapters explore the biological foundation for FWMAVs; impressive feats of flight include hovering, nimble maneuvering, and effective long-distance flight demonstrated by birds and insects. These features are mostly ascribed to their flapping wings, which produce push and lift in tandem. Researchers hope to recreate the efficiency and agility of these natural flyers in FWMAVs by studying them. [10]

2.1.2 Flight Characteristics

Many elements, like aerodynamics, flapping frequency, and wing shape, affect the flying characteristics of FWMAVs. The significance of wing stiffness and flexibility, which affect the vehicle's capacity to produce lift and thrust, is covered in the book. Furthermore, a number of flapping kinematics, including angle and stroke amplitude, are critical in determining how aerodynamically effective FWMAVs are. One essential component of contemporary FWMAVs is autonomous flight. The DelFly project places a strong emphasis on utilising artificial intelligence (AI) to increase these levels of autonomy. FWMAVs can carry out intricate tasks like obstacle recognition, navigation, and flight stabilisation thanks to AI algorithms.[10]

2.1.3 Aerodynamics

An essential component of FWMAV performance is aerodynamics. The book covers aerodynamics for both fixed-wing and flapping wings, emphasising the particular difficulties

involved in flapping flight. A thorough examination is conducted into important aerodynamic phenomena such as wake capture, leading-edge vortices, and unsteady force generation. In order to improve flying efficiency and stability, the DelFly's aerodynamic research focuses on optimising wing geometry and analysing the flow patterns during flapping. [10]

2.1.4 Case Study: The DelFly

The DelFly provides as a practical case study for comprehending the complexities of FWMAV design and implementation. The project resulted in multiple prototypes of the vehicle, all of which enhanced the autonomy, control, and performance of flight over their predecessors. The DelFly project investigates a range of configurations, such as energy storage options, actuation techniques, and designs for the wings and tail. In order to maximise the endurance and performance of FWMAVs, certain design components are essential. The DelFly Explorer, for example, has inbuilt stereo vision to improve obstacle avoidance and navigation. The DelFly project's experimental findings offer important new perspectives on the practical uses of FWMAVs as well as their future development possibilities. [10]

2.1.5 Future Directions and Challenges

The gaps identified in this literature are as follows:

- **Underexplored Image Appearance Features:** Because of computational difficulties, image appearance features are still underutilised in obstacle detection research, with most current work focusing on optic flow. More research is required to determine effective ways to extract and use these features.
- **Limited Real-world Application Testing:** Previous research emphasises that obstacle detection and turning logic have limitations, particularly in situations with low texture quality. To increase robustness and reliability, more thorough testing and algorithm adaption for a range of real-world scenarios are needed.
- **Need for Advanced Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Sensor Fusion:** It is necessary to integrate more sensors and combine multiple visual cues to improve autonomous navigation. It is necessary to create advanced AI methods, like deep learning, to enhance flight control and obstacle avoidance.

Additional research can fill up these gaps and greatly expand the capabilities and uses of the DelFly device, increasing its adaptability and effectiveness in real-world situations.

2.2 A Note on the Electromechanical Design of a Robotic Hummingbird

2.2.1 Introduction

Bio-inspired robotics and micro aerial vehicles (MAVs) have expressed great interest in robotic birds, especially those that replicate the hummingbird's flapping wing action. Hummingbirds are a great model for these robots because of their complex flight mechanisms and ability to hover. The electromechanical design of robotic hummingbirds is examined in this study of the literature, with an emphasis on current developments, significant obstacles, and potential future paths. [11]

2.2.2 Flapping Wing Mechanisms

A key feature of robotic hummingbirds is its flapping wing mechanism, which is modeled after the biomechanics of actual birds. Simple linkages and crank mechanisms were used in earlier versions to simulate the flapping motion. Nevertheless, these systems had to contend with issues including restricted flapping frequency, excessive friction, and mechanical complexity. A notable development is the switch to gear transmission systems, as demonstrated by the COLIBRI project. These technologies improve overall efficiency by lowering friction, making assembly simpler, and enabling lubrication. For lift generation and energy efficiency, flapping wings must operate aerodynamically well. To maximize performance, studies have looked into different wing shapes, materials, and designs. Inspired by hummingbirds in the wild, trailing edge serration has demonstrated potential to improve aerodynamic efficiency. Larger wings have been shown to provide lift at lower frequencies, requiring less energy and producing less heat—two essential factors in extending flight duration. [11]

2.2.3 Methodological Review

In robotics, experimental testing and computational modeling are commonly used in methods of investigation for hummingbirds. Various types of experimental sets are intended to assess mechanical power, lift, flapping frequency, and thermal performance. Aerodynamic property simulation and mechanical design optimisation are accomplished by computational models. A solid framework for creating effective and high-performing robotic systems is provided by the integration of these approaches. [11]

2.2.4 Summary of Key Findings

According to the literature, there have been notable developments in the electromechanical design of robotic hummingbirds. Lift production and flying endurance have been improved by switching to gear transmission systems, improving wing designs, utilising efficient battery combinations, and carefully choosing motors. Research is still being done, though, on issues including improving control systems, reducing friction, and maximizing power-to-weight ratios. [11]

2.2.5 Future Directions and Challenges

Despite the literature being useful, there are certain topics which require further research:

- **Advanced Materials:** More research into cutting-edge materials that offer improved durability and strength-to-weight ratios is necessary.
- **Autonomous Control Systems:** It is still difficult to create autonomous control systems that can adjust to changing flight conditions.
- **Energy Efficiency:** To further increase flight times, more work must be done to improve the power systems' energy efficiency.

2.3 Design Optimisation and System Integration of Robotic Hummingbird

2.3.1 Introduction and Background

Flapping Wing Micro Air Vehicles (FWMAVs) are inspired by the extraordinary stability and agility of hummingbirds and insects in their design and development. Their adeptness at executing quick movements without sacrificing stability makes them an excellent model for engineers working on micro-scale flight solutions. Achieving a balance between mechanical complexity, controllability, weight, power efficiency, and power efficiency under strict size, weight, and power (SWaP) restrictions is a challenge in the development of FWMAVs. [12]

2.3.2 Historical Development and Challenges

Lift generation and mechanism design of FWMAVs have been the focus of several studies. Pilot stability and control were achieved to varied degrees in early versions using motor-driven mechanisms and piezoelectric actuators. But there's still a big obstacle to overcome when it comes to integrating onboard electronics and power systems, particularly for FWMAVs that are on the sub-gram scale. [12]

2.3.3 Prototyping and Experimental Validation

The study involved three different prototypes to evaluate the design optimisation:

- Prototype 1: Rigid wings, 160mm wing span, mass 7.5g, max lift 12g
- Prototype 2: Flexible wings, 170mm wing span, mass 12g, max lift 20g
- Prototype 3: Similar to Prototype 2, except with a lower centre of gravity and mass 10.5g

Performance testing with varying payload conditions, high-speed video analysis of wing kinematics, and liftoff demonstrations were all part of the experimental evaluation process. [12]

2.3.4 Future Directions and Challenges

- Control Algorithms: Better control algorithms and integration strategies could lead to even more improvements in FWMAV design.
- Increased Autonomy: In order to achieve increased autonomy and performance in micro-scale flight, future research may concentrate on improved onboard processing capabilities, more effective power systems, and advanced materials. [12]

2.4 Kinematic and Aerodynamic Enhancement of a Robotic Hummingbird

2.4.1 Introduction and Motivation

Similar to the COLIBRI project, the development of robotic hummingbirds comes from the combination of advanced engineering and biology. The development of micro air vehicles (MAVs) with the ability to hover and fly with agility has been influenced by our growing understanding of the unstable aerodynamic mechanics of flapping-wing insects and birds. In terms of efficiency and performance, robotic hummingbirds still lag behind their biological counterparts despite notable developments. [13]

2.4.2 State of the Art in Flapping-Wing Micro Air Vehicles (FWMAVs)

The following significant projects have impacted the advancement of MAVs:

- Delfly: An MAV that emphasises agility and lightweight design in order to replicate the flight of insects
- Harvard's Robobee: A robot the size of an insect that can take off vertically, demonstrating the future potential of miniature flapping-wing robots
- AeroVironment's Nano Hummingbird: A tailless flapping-wing MAV intended for precision and steadiness in flight

These projects demonstrate the many methods used in MAV design, with an emphasis on various elements like weight, size, and control systems. But there are still obstacles in the way of matching the performance of real hummingbirds, especially when it comes to weight efficiency and frequency of flapping. [13]

2.4.3 Experimental and Computational Studies

Many studies on flapping flight are restricted to rigid wings with fixed kinematics, despite advancements in computational fluid dynamics (CFD). The COLIBRI project's emphasis on flexible wings increases complexity while also offering the possibility of increased aerodynamic efficiency:

- Aeroelastic Interaction: Aeroelastic interactions, including both chordwise and spanwise deflections, in flapping elastic wings have been studied.
- Lift Enhancement: The clap-and-fling effect is one of the phenomena that has been researched for its ability to increase lift in MAVs. [13]

2.4.4 Future Directions and Challenges

A number of obstacles must be overcome in order to continue improving robotic hummingbirds like COLIBRI. These include:

- Weight Reduction: Improving flying efficiency requires achieving a weight that is similar to that of living hummingbirds.
- Advanced Control Systems: Creating increasingly complex control systems to manage the intricacies of flexible wing aerodynamics and guarantee steady hovering.
- Material Innovations: Enhancing wing flexibility and lowering power usage while maintaining structural integrity by utilising new materials

2.5 COLIBRI: A hovering flapping twin-wing robot

2.5.1 Background and Motivation

Understanding the unstable aerodynamic systems that allow insects and hummingbirds to produce amazing forces with their flapping wings has come a long way over the last few decades. This understanding, together with developments in the miniaturisation of avionics and the increasing interest with drones, has fueled the creation of biomimetic robots. [14]

2.5.2 Design and Construction of COLIBRI

The COLIBRI robot has a wingspan of 21 cm, a flapping frequency of 22 Hz, and weighs 22g. It uses wing twist modulation, an active stabilisation device, to adjust pitch and roll. Through the use of a closed-loop proportional-derivative (PD) controller, this device reorganises airflow to change the mean lift vector. Yaw control is passive, whereas vertical position can be actively adjusted by varying the frequency of flapping. [14]

Key Enhancements:

- **Wing Design:** The wings only have one degree of freedom, which is to flap, and camber is passively produced by aerodynamic forces. Following testing with a variety of materials and designs, polyester (Icarex) stiffened with carbon bars was used in the final prototype.
- **Flapping Mechanism:** An intricate system connected by a gear box and powered by a brushed DC motor. A thorough analysis of the flapping motion's kinematics is conducted, and the construction is exact thanks to the use of 3D printed components.
- **Control Mechanism:** Through modifying the camber distribution along the wing span, the wing twist modulation produces pitch and roll torques. In order to stabilise the robot during flight, this mechanism is essential. [14]

2.5.3 Future Directions and Challenges

Several issues are highlighted by the development of the COLIBRI robot:

- **Weight Efficiency:** Robotic hummingbirds still weigh more for a given wing length than their wild counterparts, indicating a need for more weight reduction and miniaturisation.
- **Complexity of Motion:** Since robotic wings usually have fewer degrees of freedom, mimicking the entire range of motion of genuine hummingbirds remains a substantial issue.

2.6 Learning Extreme Hummingbird Maneuvers on Flapping Wing Robots

2.6.1 Introduction

The goal of the project is to mimic hummingbirds' amazing flight talents, especially their capacity for rapid escapes and severe aerobatic manoeuvres. A 12-gram hummingbird robot with two actuators is used to do this. Through the integration of model-free reinforcement learning and model-based nonlinear control, the researchers created a hybrid control technique that allows the robot to execute evasive manoeuvres that are similar to those seen in actual hummingbirds. [15]

2.6.2 Hummingbird Maneuver Studies

Hummingbirds' quick evasive movements have been the subject of recent studies that have shed light on their dynamics. Hummingbirds use a mixture of pitch and yaw movements together with linear translation to react to visual stimuli. During these manoeuvres, hummingbirds can consume up to 4.5 times their hovering power thanks to anaerobic metabolism. To provide the required body torque, substantial wing kinematic modifications are needed. [15]

2.6.3 Hybrid Flight Control Strategy

The research uses a hybrid flight control approach that combines a model-free reinforcement learning policy for manoeuvring with model-based nonlinear control for stability. By including learned policies that can "destabilise" the system to maximise performance during manoeuvres, this method overcomes the shortcomings of model-based controllers in harsh environments. The outcomes of the experiment show how successful the hybrid control approach is. The hummingbird robot hovered, tracked a figure-of-eight trajectory, and executed quick evasive manoeuvres. The method is validated by the fact that the manoeuvres accomplished are similar to those of actual hummingbirds. [15]

2.6.4 Future Directions and Challenges

The key challenges in this literature are:

- **Handling Modeling Uncertainties and Robustness:** There are major issues associated with unstable and underactuated body dynamics, parameter uncertainty, and unsteady flapping-wing aerodynamics. Particularly when performing intense manoeuvres and altering trim conditions, the current controllers are not robust enough to handle these uncertainties.
- **Real-world Testing and Validation:** There has been little experimental validation of control algorithms in real-world circumstances. To make sure that the training policies and control techniques function well and robustly under a range of shocks and uncertainties, more real-world testing is required.

2.7 Robotic Hummingbird Axial Dynamics and Control near Hovering: A Simulation Model

2.7.1 Flight Dynamics

Cycle-Averaged Longitudinal Dynamics

MAVs with flapping wings can be represented as rigid bodies with weakly linked lateral and longitudinal dynamics. Assuming that the fast changes in aerodynamic forces throughout a flapping cycle appear as noise, cycle-averaged aerodynamic forces and moments can simplify the dynamics near hovering for the COLIBRI robot. [16]

Stabilisation and Control

The COLIBRI robot's pitch and roll axes are naturally unsteady and need to be actively controlled, where as the yaw axis is stable. The primary damping mechanism is the wings fluttering, which can be represented by a point force that is proportionate to the centre of drag's velocity. With this method, the aerodynamic forces along the lateral axis are guaranteed to self-balance during a flapping cycle. [16]

2.7.2 Attitude Reconstruction and Control Systems

Complementary Filter and Kalman Filter

The complementary filter and the full-state dynamic observer (Kalman filter) are the two main techniques for reconstructing attitude. The complimentary filter operates under the presumption that the robot frame's accelerometer provides information about the direction of the gravity vector. By incorporating the robot dynamics into the attitude estimation process, the Kalman filter on the other hand, allows for better hovering control and the reconstruction of linear velocity. [16]

IMU and Control Board

A six-axis IMU with a proprietary algorithm was utilised for attitude reconstruction in the first COLIBRI robot. To increase noise rejection and stability, a modern control board with an ARM processor and twin IMU sensors (six and nine axes) has been designed. This new board has a Bluetooth link and is designed to deal with the noise created by wing flapping. [16]

2.7.3 Future Directions and Challenges

- **Autonomy and Efficiency:** Improving flight autonomy is an important challenge in the development of flapping wing MAVs. Even with the notable improvements in efficiency made in recent designs, robotic hummingbirds still weigh more than their real-life counterparts. Future studies seek to make these robots lighter and more energy-efficient. [16]
- **Noise Rejection and Stability:** Maintaining stability while dealing with flapping noise is still a crucial topic of concern. It is important to carefully weigh the trade-off between noise rejection and stability margins, and more flight testing should provide additional information on how to best achieve both goals. [16]

2.8 Design, Development and Flight-Testing of a Robotic Hummingbird

2.8.1 Mechanism Design

The robotic hummingbird imitates the flying mechanics of actual hummingbirds by using a pair of flapping wings. An precise actuator mechanism powers the wings, enabling exact control over the frequency and amplitude of flapping. The robotic hummingbird was built with lightweight materials so that it could maintain flight while carrying the required power sources and electronics. [17]

2.8.2 Control Systems

The integration of sensors and feedback loops by the control system ensures stability and manoeuvrability while in flight. Based on sensor data, advanced algorithms were created to regulate the wing movements and modify flying characteristics in real-time. [17]

2.8.3 Aerodynamic Performance

A wind tunnel and free flight scenarios were used to evaluate the robotic hummingbird's aerodynamic performance. According to the results, the robotic hummingbird was able to perform agile movements and stable hovering, just like a real hummingbird. The design was optimised for performance and efficiency by taking precise measurements of lift, thrust, and power consumption. [17]

2.8.4 Future Directions and Challenges

- **Complexity of Unsteady Aerodynamics:** Although understanding of unstable aerodynamic phenomena such as leading-edge vortices (LEVs) has advanced, it is still difficult to precisely simulate these effects. These intricate interactions are frequently oversimplified in current computational models, which may cause differences between simulated and actual performance.

- **Material Durability and Flexibility:** Durability and light weight must be balanced in the materials used to make flexible wings. It's possible that current materials don't offer the ideal balance of weight, flexibility, and strength needed for extended use and frequent flapping cycles.
- **Power Consumption:** Flapping-wing flight requires a lot of energy. The goal is to build lightweight power sources and actuation systems that can provide sustained energy for long flight periods. The energy density required for extended flights may not be provided by current battery technologies.

2.9 From Studying Real Hummingbirds to Designing Hummingbird-Like Robots

2.9.1 Bio-Inspiration and Mechanisms

Hummingbirds possess exceptional flight abilities, including the ability to hover, accelerate quickly, and make nimble movements. Their wing kinematics and aerodynamic forces interact intricately in their wing flapping mechanics. The flapping motion of the wings was the main focus of early attempts to imitate hummingbird flight. AeroVironment's Nano Hummingbird proved that a comparable wing-flapping mechanism could be used to achieve steady hovering. [18]

2.9.2 Mechanical Design and Actuation

Robotic hummingbirds are often built with lightweight materials like carbon fibre composites and advanced polymers for their bodies and wings. These materials offer the strength-to-weight ratio required for long-term flight. Piezoelectric actuators, smart materials, and direct-drive motors are some of the actuator systems used in flapping wing robots. Regarding weight, control accuracy, and power economy, each system has benefits and trade-offs. [18]

2.9.3 Control Systems and Flight Dynamics

Robotic hummingbirds' control systems have to handle the unstable dynamics of flapping flight. Several control algorithms have been built by researchers to maintain the robot's stability while it hovers and manoeuvres. In order to offer real-time feedback on the orientation and location of the robot, sensors like gyroscopes, accelerometers, and vision sensors are integrated into the robotic systems. Sensor data is used by sophisticated control systems, like as Kalman filters and complementing filters, to dynamically modify the wing kinematics. Performing intricate manoeuvres and preserving stability depend on this integration. [18]

2.9.4 Experimental Validation and Performance Evaluation

In experimental validation, the robotic hummingbirds are put to the test in controlled settings, like wind tunnels, in order to measure aerodynamic forces and verify computer models. For robotic hummingbirds, lift-to-weight ratio, power consumption, flight time, and manoeuvrability are important performance measures. Research has indicated that attaining equilibrium among these metrics is crucial for maximising the robot's efficiency. [18]

2.9.5 Future Directions and Challenges

- **Scaling and Miniaturisation:** One of the biggest challenges in the development of robotic hummingbirds is reducing the component size without sacrificing functionality. Miniaturisation of power systems, actuators, and sensors continues to be an important area of research. Subsequent investigations endeavour to further reduce the mass and dimensions of these robots while preserving or improving their ability to fly.
- **Autonomy and Intelligence:** Creating more complex control algorithms and incorporating artificial intelligence for decision-making and environment adaptability are necessary to increase the autonomy of robotic hummingbirds. Future research should focus on autonomous navigation and interaction with complicated environments, as these areas may find use in surveillance, environmental monitoring, and search and rescue operations. [18]

2.10 Geometric Flight Control of a Hovering Robotic Hummingbird

2.10.1 Wing Design and Materials

FWMAV wing designs have changed dramatically over time, with a focus on mimicking the robust, light structure of natural wings. Material science developments have made it possible to create composite materials with excellent strength-to-weight ratios. For example, lightweight polymers and carbon fibre are frequently utilised in the construction of artificial wings. Moreover, the application of bio-inspired design concepts has resulted in advancements in wing morphology, augmenting the manoeuvrability and aerodynamic efficiency of FWMAVs. [19]

2.10.2 Control Systems and Algorithms

One of the most difficult parts of developing FWMAVs is achieving stable and controlled flying. To address the nonlinear and extremely dynamic character of flapping flight, researchers have looked into a variety of control techniques. More advanced techniques have been investigated to improve aircraft stability and manoeuvrability, including adaptive control, feedback linearisation, and model predictive control. [19]

2.10.3 Nonlinear Controller Design for Robotic Hummingbirds

The paper focuses on the design and implementation of a nonlinear controller for a robotic hummingbird that hovers. Using this method, the vehicle's orientation and position may be precisely controlled by utilising the system's geometric features. An effective foundation for handling the nonlinearities present in flapping wing flight is provided by geometric control theory, which has been thoroughly researched in the context of robotic systems. [19]

2.10.4 System Identification and Modeling

Identifying and modelling systems accurately is essential to creating control techniques that work. To simulate the dynamics of FWMAVs, researchers have used a range of methodologies, such as experimental investigations, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations, and analytical approaches. By capturing the fundamentals of flapping flight, these models make it possible to create controllers that can anticipate and adjust for a vehicle's behaviour in real time. [19]

2.10.5 Future Directions and Challenges

- **Computational Load and High-Frequency Noise:** Although effective, the Kalman-based algorithms employed for sensor fusion have a large computing load, especially at high sampling rates, making onboard implementation difficult. Precise orientation determination is challenging because the flapping motion generates high-frequency noise that degrades IMU sensor fusion methods.
- **Control Torque and Authority:** The existing design limits the capacity to generate adequate control authority, particularly for yaw torque, which impacts the FWMAV's overall stability and manoeuvrability.
- **Thrust Production:** To increase thrust and improve performance, new approaches to direct/indirect angle of attack control and motor current regulation must be investigated. [19]

2.11 Main Challenges

Based on the literature review of these sources, the main challenges which appear to be universal are:

- Scaling and weight of the model
- The material used
- Autonomy
- Efficiency
- Limited real world testing

By identifying the main challenges in existing research, it is now possible to determine which factors are to be considered and incorporated in the design of the FWMAV and as a result, ensuring the best outcome in the testing phase.

Chapter 3

Theoretical Framework

3.1 Aerodynamics

Hummingbirds' aerodynamic intricacy is a result of their exceptional agility, ability to hover, and ability to fly in all directions. The hummingbird's unique figure-eight wing motion is the key to its abilities. Hummingbirds are unique among birds in that they generate lift on both the upstroke and downstroke, which enables them to hover in place. Most other birds only generate lift on the downstroke.

FIGURE 3.1: The Hummingbird Figure-Eight Motion
[20]

Because of its flexible shoulder joints, the hummingbird may twist its wing backwards during the upstroke to achieve an angle of attack appropriate for producing lift. To produce more lift during the upstroke, the hummingbird can also alter the camber of its wings. [21] The hummingbird's extremely efficient flight is further aided by its lightweight body and unique feathers, which improve airflow and reduce drag. Hummingbirds' exceptional ability to manoeuvre through the air allows them to not only hover but also dart quickly between flowers, execute precise aerial manoeuvres, and even fly backwards.

3.2 Wing Kinematics and Unsteady Aerodynamics

A hummingbird's wing has 3 degrees-of-freedom(DOF); the main wing flapping motion (up and down), the wing rotation and the slight forward and backward movement relative to the body. Because of this, flight dynamics can be precisely controlled, especially in low Reynolds number situations where traditional aerodynamic concepts are less successful. Additionally, they use trailing edge vortices (TEVs) and leading edge vortices (LEVs) to increase lift and thrust while preserving stability. These are examples of unsteady aerodynamics. They frequently fly with wings that are corrugated, which offers better structural resilience to withstand the pressures encountered during flight, but does not always improve aerodynamic efficiency. [22]

FIGURE 3.2: Typical Hummingbird Wing [23]

3.3 Wing Morphology

FIGURE 3.3: Hummingbird forelimb skeleton in hovering flight. (A) Position at mid-downstroke. (B) Position at mid-upstroke.

[24]

When compared to other birds, hummingbirds have wing morphology that is different because their handwings are much larger, accounting for approximately 75% of their wing area, whereas most other birds' handwings only make up about 50%. This is due to the smaller upper arm and forearm bones. Additionally, only the highly mobile shoulder can produce motion; the wrist and elbow are immobile. Both the downstroke and the upstroke of the wing are powered by strong muscles, the depressor and elevator, respectively. Because of this unequal lift production between the downstroke and upstroke, the depressor weighs twice as much as the lift. Roughly thirty percent of the body weight is composed of hummingbird muscles. [25]

Chapter 4

Prototype Designs

4.1 Design 1

FIGURE 4.1: Design 1

This was the initial design. It incorporated the flapping wings motion through the use of rotating gears in the midsection of the bird. The key features of the design are:

- **Simple Wing Mechanism:** The flapping motion of the wings was produced using a basic crankshaft arrangement, making the mechanism rather straightforward. This approach was selected in order to assess the practicability of the wing movement and to comprehend the associated aerodynamic forces. The single motor that propelled the crankshaft had the wings bolted straight to it. Although the flapping motion could be produced consistently with this system, the flapping frequency and wing angle could not be accurately controlled.

- **Rigid Structure:** The purpose of the rigid design was to offer a solid testing platform for the flapping mechanism without having to worry about excessive flexibility or material failure that might hinder the flapping motion.
- **Focus on Stability:** Even though it was simple, Design 1 had a balanced centre of gravity to improve flying stability. But instead of using complex control systems for active stabilisation, the design relied on the symmetry and mass distribution of the structure's intrinsic stability.

The goal of Design 1 was to provide a proof of concept. The project started with a straightforward, reliable design in order to validate the fundamentals of flapping wing mechanics and to pinpoint the difficulties in developing a bio-inspired FWMAV. The robotic hummingbird was eventually improved upon and made more capable by applying what was learnt from designing this prototype.

4.2 Design 2

FIGURE 4.2: Design 2
[26]

Design 2 improved flying performance and manoeuvrability by adding a number of significant changes, building on the lessons learnt from Design 1. The key features of the design are:

- **Improved Wing Design:** An improved linkage system that provided greater control over the wing's angle of attack was incorporated into the wing mechanism update. More stable and controlled flight was made possible by this improvement, which also made it possible to modify the flapping frequency and generate lift more effectively.
- **Flexible Wing Structure:** Design 2 added wings with a more flexible structure as opposed to Design 1's inflexible wings. The goal of this flexibility was to replicate the hummingbird wings' natural motion, which would improve energy transfer and increase lift production when flapping. The design's overall durability was improved by the flexible wings, which also reduced the mechanical stress on the joints.
- **Increased Stability:** Design 2 improved the body's stability during hovering and forward flight by having a more balanced centre of gravity and making small structural changes. Compared to Design 1, where stability posed the biggest obstacle, this was a major improvement.

- **Slider Mechanism:** With varied wing motion, this slider improved control over the frequency and amplitude of flapping. Additionally, the slider mechanism made it easier to switch between various flying modes, such as hovering and forward flight.
- **Lower Centre of Gravity:** The design distributed the body's mass to create a lower centre of gravity, which improved stability. Balance during flight would also be enhanced by this modification, particularly while switching between different manoeuvres. The reduced centre of gravity was critical for staying stable during quick changes in direction or speed.

Design 3 intended to improve upon the capabilities presented in Design 2 by adding more sophisticated mechanical and aerodynamic aspects. The implementation of the slider mechanism, as well as stability improvements, were crucial steps towards developing a robotic hummingbird capable of replicating the agility and control found in natural hummingbirds.

4.4 Design 4

This design was inspired by Peter Wang's flapping wing mechanism design shown below, which is renowned for being able to accurately and successfully replicate the flight of actual hummingbirds.

FIGURE 4.5: Peter Wang's Flapping Wing Mechanism Design [27]

FIGURE 4.6: Design 4

The key features of the design are:

- **Advanced Wing Dynamics:** Design 4's wings were intended to be extremely dynamic, with the ability to modify wing twist and angle of attack in addition to flapping frequency. This will make it possible for the robotic hummingbird to precisely execute a variety of difficult flight functions, such as backward flight, quick direction changes, hovering, as well as following the figure-eight pattern.
- **Robust and Lightweight Structure:** Because Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS) would be used throughout the whole structure prototype, it will be lightweight and have the required durability. The design prioritises weight reduction without sacrificing structural integrity, ensuring that every component was securely connected.

Using the most effective elements and knowledge gained from past prototypes, Design 4 was the result of all prior design efforts. The sophisticated control systems and wing dynamics represented the most advanced aspects of what was possible with this project, while the inspiration from Peter Wang's mechanism offered a verified base upon which the design was developed.

4.5 Material Properties

In this project, the prototype components of the robotic hummingbird were all 3D printed using ABS. ABS is a thermoplastic polymer that offers exceptional strength, flexibility, and durability, allowing it to be a perfect option for constructing a sturdy yet lightweight model. This was chosen after comparing a few different materials such as ABS, nylon and carbon fiber. Table 4.1 shows the strengths and limitations for the different materials.

TABLE 4.1: Material Properties for 3D Printing

Material	Strengths	Limitations
ABS	"Good mechanical properties that make it strong, durable, and reliable", "Affordable", "Withstand high temperatures compared to most inexpensive thermoplastics" [28]	"Printed parts are prone to warping", "ABS becomes discolored and often brittle" after prolonged exposure to ultraviolet (UV) radiation, "releases toxic, foul-smelling volatile organic compounds (VOCs) while printing" [28]
Nylon	"Tough and partially flexible", "High impact resistance", "No unpleasant odor while printing", "Good abrasion resistance" [29]	"Prone to Warping", "Air-tight storage required to prevent water absorption", "Improperly dried filaments can cause printing defects", "Not suitable for moist and humid environments" [29]
Carbon Fiber	"Strong and Lightweight", "Heat Resistance", "Stiffness" [30]	"Expensive", "Brittle" [30]

Chapter 5

Testing and Results

After deciding that design 4 would be the best design to move forward with, a computer aided design (CAD) was required to design the prototype and run a simulation. The software used to CAD the chosen design was PTC Creo.

FIGURE 5.1: CAD of Design 4

5.1 Simulation Results

PTC Creo simulations were used to thoroughly evaluate the final design. The intended function of the flapping wing mechanism was verified by the simulations. The wings moved correctly, producing lift and resembling the intended figure-eight pattern—an essential component in simulating a hummingbird’s ability to hover. The mechanism demonstrated potential for steady flight in the simulation, with the wing kinematics operating at peak efficiency. The lift produced in the simulation aligned with the design objectives, and the overall aerodynamics indicated that, if properly executed in a physical model, the design might accomplish hovering and agile flight manoeuvres.

5.2 3D Printing and Assembly

The components were carefully 3D printed using ABS as it offers a good mix of strength, flexibility, and being easy to print (see Appendix A for the 3D printed components). But as each component came together, it was clear that there was an uneven distribution of weight. The wings caused a shift in centre of gravity since they were heavier and larger than expected. The prototype became unstable overall as a result of this imbalance, being made worse by the absence of a rigid external structure to support the mechanism. In addition, although the components mostly fit together as intended, some of them had their structural integrity impeded by how thin they were. These thin parts shattered under pressure during assembly, especially when the wings and flapping mechanism were fitted. This weakness added to the overall instability of the design in addition to compromising the prototype's structural integrity. The assembly procedure brought to light the difficulties in converting an electronic design into a tangible model, particularly when handling intricate moving components.

FIGURE 5.2: Part of the Structure Cracking Due to the Pressure

5.3 Physical Testing

The physical testing phase was significantly limited due to the instability that became apparent during assembly. It was hard to carry out controlled experiments or collect useful information about the flight performance because of this instability. Nevertheless, the preliminary testing efforts yielded important information about the mechanical issues that need to be resolved. It became evident that lift-off was not possible without sufficient support because the forces produced by the flapping wings were insufficient to offset the weight of the wings. This emphasised how crucial it is to include both structural reinforcements and material considerations in subsequent modifications.

Chapter 6

Discussion

6.1 Analysis of Simulation vs. Physical Prototype

There were notable differences between the physical prototype and the simulation results. The design operated as anticipated in PTC Creo's virtual environment, exhibiting fine control over wing motions and a steady aerodynamic profile. But moving from a virtual model to an actual prototype revealed a number of practical difficulties. The biggest problem was that the heavy wings made it impossible for the design to stay stable. This brought to light a crucial error made during the modelling stage, where material characteristics like as weight distribution and mechanical connections were not properly taken into consideration. The investigation revealed that, although simulations are a great tool for verifying designs at the outset, physical restrictions and in-person testing are also necessary to make sure a design is practical.

6.2 Design Limitations

The physical characteristics of the prototype were the main source of the existing design's constraints. Due to their weight in relation to the rest of the structure, the heavy wings—which were meant to provide the required lift—became a problem. This problem was made worse by the absence of an external frame to support the mechanism; without a structure, the forces produced by the flapping motion could not be absorbed or distributed. Furthermore, even though the ABS material was sturdy, it's possible that it didn't offer the ideal combination of stiffness and flexibility, which added to the instability. This section also takes into account the constraints of the selected materials and makes the suggestion that, in order to attain the necessary performance, other materials or manufacturing techniques could be needed.

6.3 Potential Improvements

In the future, a number of changes could be made to increase the design's performance and stability. Initially, a redesign of the wings to make them lighter may require reducing their size or utilising lighter materials, including carbon fibre composites or even cutting-edge polymers that have comparable strength but less weight. The incorporation of an outside support system will also be essential. It is possible that this construction will protect sensitive parts, stabilise the mechanism, and better distribute the weight throughout the MAV. The internal mechanical links could also be improved, perhaps by using lighter, more sophisticated materials for the gears and connectors or by optimising the design to better distribute the weight.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

7.1 Summary of Findings

The aim of this research was to close the gap between the technical difficulties involved in developing a working FWMAV and the biological inspiration of hummingbird flying. The design process revealed that the proposed system potentially could accomplish the intricate flight dynamics seen in real hummingbirds, and this conclusion was reinforced by extensive simulations conducted in PTC Creo. Nevertheless, substantial issues with weight distribution and structural stability were found in the physical prototype, which made testing unsuccessful.

7.2 Implications for Future Work

The difficulties this project faced serve as guidelines for next studies and improvements. Future work should mostly address the stability and weight issues. This could entail investigating new substances and fabrication methods that better meet the requirements of a flapping wing MAV in addition to modifying the existing mechanism. In order to achieve steady flight, it is also necessary to integrate an external support structure or a more advanced stabilisation mechanism. In order to guarantee that the actual prototypes more closely match the simulated models, future work should also take into account doing more thorough simulations that take material attributes and assembly limitations into account.

7.3 Final Thoughts

This effort has contributed significantly to our understanding of flapping wing MAVs and its promise for bio-inspired flying, despite encountered challenges. The knowledge gained from this experience emphasises the value of iterative design, in which every obstacle is seen as a chance for improvement and creativity. Future iterations of this study could open up opportunities for more sophisticated, capable, and stable MAVs by resolving the limits that have been found and investigating new design approaches.

Appendix A

3D Printed Prototype Parts

The following parts were 3D printed using Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS).

FIGURE A.1: Prototype Wings

FIGURE A.2: Prototype Gears for Wing Mechanism

FIGURE A.3: Prototype Connectors

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